

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Smokers' support for the ban on sale of slim cigarettes in six European countries: findings from the EUREST-PLUS ITC Europe surveys [version 1; peer review: 1 approved with reservations, 1 not approved]

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Abstract

Background: Efforts to regulate tobacco products and reduce consumption in the European Union (EU) include the European Tobacco Products Directive (TPD), which went into force in May 2016. Despite the initial discussion to include a ban on sale of slim cigarettes, it was excluded in the final TPD. The main goal of this study was to examine support for a ban on slim cigarettes among smokers in six European Countries.

Methods: Data from the 2018 (Wave 2) International Tobacco Control Policy Evaluation Project 6 European Country (ITC 6E) EUREST-PLUS project survey, a cross sectional study of adult smokers (n=5592) from Germany, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, and Spain, was analysed. Descriptive statistics were used to estimate support for a ban on slim cigarettes by sociodemographic characteristics and smoking behaviors. Logistic regression analysis was used to examine factors associated with support for a ban on slim cigarettes and perceptions of harm.

Results: Support for a ban on slims varied across countries, with highest support in Romania (33.8%), and lowest in Greece (18.0%). Female smokers (OR=0.77; 95%CI=0.66-0.90, daily smokers (OR=0.59; 95%CI=0.42-0.83), menthol smokers (OR=0.56; 95%CI=0.36-0.87), and smokers who did not have plans to quit within next six months (OR=0.45; 95%CI=0.36-0.57) had significantly lower odds of supporting a ban on slim cigarettes. Overall, 20% of smokers perceived slim cigarettes as less harmful than regular cigarettes.

Conclusions: Support for a ban of slim cigarettes was relatively low among smokers, while misperceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful is high, particularly among countries where slim cigarette use is more prevalent. Findings support a ban on slim cigarettes to reduce misperceptions around slim cigarettes being less harmful.

Keywords

Tobacco Products Directive, slim cigarettes, tobacco policy, European Union

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Introduction

Around 700,000 people die annually in the European Union (EU) due to tobacco use¹. Despite recent efforts undertaken to reduce misperceptions of tobacco products, implementation of tobacco control policies is still needed².

Within the EU countries, around half of smokers use cigarettes with special characteristics such as additive-free or organic, light, menthol flavor, slim, etc. Slim cigarettes are consumed by around 5% of EU smokers¹. Slim cigarettes have a diameter of 5 or 6 millimeters and a length that varies from 68–121 mm according to the category (from regular to extra-long)³. Tobacco companies have historically targeted women by promoting slim cigarettes as stylish and feminine³. A qualitative study among young women concluded that slim cigarettes are perceived to be correlated with glamour, cleanliness, and safety⁴. Similarly, in a Scottish study, slim cigarettes were considered as lovely, pretty, fun, cool, and cute by teenage girls and young women⁵. A Polish study among young population aged 13–19 years (secondary and high school students) found that that slim cigarettes were perceived to be less harmful⁶. In light of such misperceptions, supporters (both smokers and non-smokers) of a ban on slim cigarettes argued that slim cigarettes are as harmful as normal cigarettes but that their promotion and design features reinforce smoker's misconceptions on these products to be less harmful and, therefore, make quitting smoking more difficult.

The revised EU Tobacco Products Directive (TPD) came into force in May 2016. The TPD aims to improve protection of the health of EU citizens from the harms of tobacco⁷. The main objective of the TPD provisions was to reduce misperceptions around reduced harm often associated with special characteristics of tobacco products. Such features of cigarettes and roll-your-own tobacco banned under the TPD include characterizing flavors, misleading labels, packs resembling a food or cosmetic product and pack sizes less than 20 cigarettes or 30g of tobacco, but did not include information on banning slim cigarettes. Population support for tobacco control policies is an important determinant of successful policy implementation. However, there is a lack of data on the factors that are associated with harm perceptions and support for a slim cigarettes ban in the EU. Given that the TPD implementation report is being prepared in 2021, it is important to understand support for banning slim cigarettes. The main goal of this study was to examine support for a ban on slim cigarettes among a representative sample of smokers in six EU countries.

Methods

The survey protocols and all materials, including the survey questionnaires, information letter and consent, were cleared for ethics by the ethics research committee at the University of Waterloo (Ontario, Canada, No. 21262), and ethics committees in Germany (Ethikkommission der Medizinischen Fakultät Heidelberg, No. DV-097-160401), Greece (Medical School, University of Athens - Research and Ethics Committee, No. 156023993), Hungary (Medical Research Council – Scientific and Research Committee, No. 46344-2/2017/EKY), Poland (State College of Higher Vocational Education - Committee and

Dean of the Department of Health Care and Life Sciences, No. dnia 22.09.2017 r), Romania (Iuliu Hatieganu University of Medicine and Pharmacy, No. 155), and Spain (Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Bellvitge, Hospital Universitari de Bellvitge, Catalonia, PR100/16). Once a respondent was selected, an information letter was provided and consent was taken. Informed written consent for participation and publication of data was obtained at the time of data collection, in which participants were informed that, “All personal information you provide is treated as strictly confidential, subject to legal requirements and limitations. It will be held in secure storage and password protected at the University of Waterloo, Canada and only be accessed by this research team. Any identifying information about you will be removed before the data are securely stored, so that your answers cannot be linked back to you. After two years, the survey data, but not your name or other identifying information, will be shared with authorized researchers in other countries, as it will be used to make comparisons of smoking behaviour and attitudes across countries.”

Data came from the 2018 (Wave 2) International Tobacco Control Evaluation Project 6 European Country (ITC 6E) Survey, a cohort study of 6,027 adult smokers (aged 18+ years) who reported having smoked at least 100 cigarettes in their lifetime and smoked at least monthly from Germany, Greece, Hungary, Poland, Romania, and Spain. These respondents consisted of two sample types: (1) re-contacted (cohort) respondents (n=3,195) from Wave 1 of the ITC 6E Survey who were followed up regardless of their current smoking status (retention rates ranged from 36% in Hungary to 71% in Germany and Spain, with an average of 53% for the full sample). Participants were recruited via multi-stage stratified random sampling. Sampling was based on geographic strata created according to Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS) regions and degree of urbanisation; and (2) new respondents (current smokers) to replenish those who were lost to attrition. The replenishment sample (n=2,832) was recruited from newly selected households, and approached in the same manner as Wave 1, with the random-walk procedure beginning at a new (random) starting point. Smokers followed from Wave 1 who had quit smoking by Wave 2 were excluded from this analysis.

Face-to-face interviews were conducted from February to May 2018. After providing written consent, respondents completed the survey via a computer-assisted personal interview conducted in each country's official language. The ITC 6E Survey is part of the European Commission Horizon-2020 funded study European Regulatory Science on Tobacco: Policy Implementation to Reduce Lung Diseases (EUREST_PLUS-HCO-06-2015), which aimed to evaluate the impact of the EU TPD⁸. Further details about the study methodology are provided elsewhere^{9–12}.

The primary outcome of this study, support for a ban on slim cigarettes, was assessed with the question: “Would you support or oppose a law that banned all slim cigarettes, that is, those cigarettes that are slimmer in size than regular

cigarettes?” (support; oppose; don’t know). Different demographic characteristics such as age, gender, degree of urbanization, education level, household income, etc. were considered as independent variables.

Descriptive statistics were used to estimate support for a ban on slim cigarettes by sociodemographic characteristics and smoking behaviors. Wald χ^2 tests were used to test for an association between independent variables and support for a ban on slim cigarettes. Multivariable logistic regression was used to estimate adjusted odds ratios (OR) and the corresponding 95% confidence intervals (CI). The ‘support for a slim ban’ variable was transformed into a binary variable (supports or strongly supports vs. otherwise = oppose/strongly oppose/don’t know). Additionally, respondents stated whether they believe that slim cigarettes are less harmful than regular cigarettes (agree/strongly agree that slims are less harmful vs. neither agree nor disagree/disagree/strongly disagree/don’t know). All statistical analyses were conducted using [SAS-callable SUDAAN](#) (Version 11.0.3) to account for the complex sampling design and cross-sectional sampling weights. The analyses can be done in most software packages that handle complex data design, such as R, an open-access software, using the ‘svytable’ and ‘svyglm’ commands from the survey package.

Results

Support for a ban on slim cigarettes

Support for a ban on slims varied across the six European countries, with highest support in Romania (33.8%;

95%CI=29.2-38.8), and lowest in Greece (18.0%; 95%CI=13.7-23.3). Smokers from Romania had significantly higher odds (OR=1.66; CI%95 =1.14-2.42) of supporting a ban on slim cigarettes than smokers from Spain. Those who had a moderate income in comparison to those with high income (OR=1.33; 95%CI =1.04-1.70) were more likely to support a ban on slim cigarettes. Female smokers (OR=0.77; 95%CI=0.66-0.90; ref=males), daily smokers (OR=0.59; 95%CI=0.42-0.83; ref=non-daily smokers), menthol smokers (OR=0.56; 95%CI=0.36-0.87; ref=no usual brand), and smokers who did not have plans to quit within next six months (OR=0.45; 95%CI=0.36-0.57; ref=smokers with plans to quit in the next six months) had significantly lower odds of supporting a ban on slim cigarettes. Smokers who agreed that slim cigarettes are less harmful than regular cigarettes were more likely to support a ban on slim cigarettes compared to those who disagreed (OR=1.96, 95%CI=1.54-2.51) ([Table 1](#)).

Perceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful

Perceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful than regular cigarettes also varied significantly across the six countries, ranging from 8.1% (95%CI=5.8-11.3) among German smokers to over one-quarter among Hungarian (29.1%; 95%CI=24.0-34.8), Polish (28.9%, 95%CI=24.3-33.9), and Romanian (26.8%, 95%CI=23.0-31.1) smokers. Smokers who reported not having plans to quit within the next six months were less likely to report that slim cigarettes are less harmful compared to those with plans to quit (OR=0.73; 95%CI=0.56-0.96). Lastly, smokers who believed that their own cigarette brand is less harmful than other brands were more likely to report that slims are less

Table 1. Support for a ban on slim cigarettes among smokers from six European countries, International Tobacco Control Evaluation Project Six European Country Survey Wave 2 (2018) (N=5577).

Covariate	% Supporting Slim Ban*			Odds of Support†		Test		
	(Unwtd Freq)	%	(95% CI)	OR	(95% CI)	ChiSq	DF	p
Country								
Germany	(182 / 939)	19.2	(14.6, 24.9)	0.80	(0.50, 1.26)	22.42	5	<.001
Greece	(174 / 944)	18.0	(13.7, 23.3)	0.74	(0.48, 1.16)			
Hungary	(188 / 942)	21.7	(16.7, 27.8)	0.92	(0.61, 1.37)			
Poland	(177 / 947)	20.0	(15.5, 25.4)	0.85	(0.56, 1.29)			
Romania	(291 / 916)	33.8	(29.2, 38.8)	1.66	(1.14, 2.42)			
Spain	(193 / 889)	23.0	(18.9, 27.8)	1.00				
Urban/rural residence								
Urban	(389 / 1932)	22.1	(18.8, 25.8)	1.11	(0.80, 1.54)	1.39	2	0.498
Intermediate	(487 / 2134)	23.5	(20.5, 26.7)	1.19	(0.89, 1.60)			
Rural	(329 / 1511)	22.0	(18.3, 26.2)	1.00				
Sex								
Female	(536 / 2715)	19.9	(17.6, 22.3)	0.77	(0.66, 0.90)	11.17	1	<.001
Male	(669 / 2862)	24.7	(22.4, 27.2)	1.00				

Covariate	% Supporting Slim Ban*			Odds of Support [†]		Test		
	(Unwtd Freq)	%	(95% CI)	OR	(95% CI)	ChiSq	DF	p
Age group								
18–24	(96 / 432)	24.9	(19.7, 30.9)	1.18	(0.84, 1.64)	1.55	3	0.670
25–39	(351 / 1533)	23.4	(20.6, 26.5)	1.11	(0.90, 1.39)			
40–54	(416 / 1940)	21.9	(19.3, 24.7)	1.05	(0.85, 1.30)			
55+	(342 / 1672)	21.7	(18.9, 24.8)	1.00				
Income								
Not stated	(260 / 1543)	18.3	(15.4, 21.5)	0.85	(0.63, 1.15)	12.97	3	0.005
Low	(226 / 993)	22.8	(19.2, 26.7)	1.08	(0.80, 1.46)			
Moderate	(452 / 1800)	26.4	(23.3, 29.9)	1.33	(1.04, 1.70)			
High	(267 / 1241)	22.6	(19.1, 26.6)	1.00				
Education								
Low	(379 / 1790)	22.3	(19.3, 25.5)	1.14	(0.82, 1.58)	0.72	2	0.698
Moderate	(698 / 3126)	23.2	(20.8, 25.8)	1.12	(0.85, 1.48)			
High	(121 / 640)	19.8	(16.2, 24.0)	1.00				
Smoking status								
Daily smoker	(1135 / 5343)	22.1	(20.1, 24.3)	0.59	(0.42, 0.83)	9.23	1	0.002
Non-daily smoker	(70 / 234)	32.5	(26.5, 39.2)	1.00				
Cigarettes smoked/day								
≤ 10	(485 / 2072)	23.8	(21.3, 26.5)	0.98	(0.60, 1.59)	1.59	3	0.662
11–20	(577 / 2796)	21.7	(19.3, 24.3)	0.92	(0.60, 1.43)			
21–30	(91 / 475)	22.5	(17.6, 28.3)	1.12	(0.68, 1.85)			
31+	(46 / 214)	21.7	(14.6, 30.3)	1.00				
Flavour smoked								
Menthol	(44 / 277)	15.0	(10.6, 20.4)	0.56	(0.36, 0.87)	8.59	3	0.035
Other flavour	(20 / 115)	19.2	(10.4, 31.1)	0.78	(0.38, 1.59)			
Unflavoured	(974 / 4545)	22.6	(20.5, 24.9)	0.96	(0.73, 1.27)			
No usual brand	(167 / 640)	25.8	(21.3, 30.9)	1.00				
Smokes factory-made(FM)/roll-your-own(RYO)								
FM	(919 / 4165)	23.1	(21.0, 25.3)	1.05	(0.76, 1.44)	0.78	2	0.677
RYO	(204 / 1027)	21.7	(18.1, 25.8)	1.15	(0.80, 1.65)			
Both	(79 / 382)	19.6	(15.0, 25.1)	1.00				
Attempts to quit in past year								
Has not tried to quit in last 12 months	(989 / 4773)	21.6	(19.6, 23.8)	0.93	(0.73, 1.18)	0.39	1	0.531
Tried to quit last 12 months	(215 / 798)	28.5	(24.2, 33.1)	1.00				

Covariate	% Supporting Slim Ban*			Odds of Support†		Test		
	(Unwtd Freq)	%	(95% CI)	OR	(95% CI)	ChiSq	DF	p
Plans to quit smoking								
No plans to quit	(983 / 4966)	20.6	(18.7, 22.7)	0.45	(0.36, 0.57)	42.64	1	<.001
Plans to quit in next 6 months	(222 / 611)	39.3	(34.3, 44.6)	1.00				
Harm of own cigarette brand vs. other brands								
Don't know	(14 / 129)	12.5	(6.0, 22.2)	0.57	(0.28, 1.17)	3.49	3	0.322
A little less harmful	(191 / 803)	26.3	(22.4, 30.5)	1.09	(0.86, 1.39)			
A little more harmful	(66 / 199)	32.6	(25.3, 40.8)	1.17	(0.79, 1.73)			
No different	(932 / 4444)	21.8	(19.6, 24.1)	1.00				
Slim cigarettes are less harmful than regular cigarettes								
Don't know	(80 / 532)	17.5	(13.6, 22.1)	0.78	(0.57, 1.07)	37.80	3	<.001
Agree	(402 / 1190)	32.9	(28.7, 37.3)	1.96	(1.54, 2.51)			
Neither	(264 / 1249)	22.0	(18.6, 25.7)	1.18	(0.92, 1.50)			
Disagree	(457 / 2589)	19.2	(16.8, 21.8)	1.00				

* Weighted percent

† Odds ratios from a weighted multivariable logistic regression model including all covariates listed in table.

Unwtd freq – unweighted frequency; CI – confidence interval; OR, odds ratio; ChiSq, chi-square statistic; DF – degrees of freedom.

harmful compared to those who perceived no difference in harm between their own and others' brand (OR=1.77; 95%CI=1.39-2.24) (Table 2).

Discussion

This study has found that approximately 20% of smokers supported a ban on slim cigarettes. Country, gender, daily/non-daily smoking status, and quitting plans were key correlates of supporting a ban on slim cigarettes. Women were less likely to support a ban on slims than men, which is not surprising given that slim cigarettes have historically been specifically marketed to females by the tobacco industry¹³. The fact that slim cigarettes are associated with perceptions of glamour, cleanliness, and safety⁴, which are mainly characteristics of femininity, may be the reason^{14,15}. According to the 2017 Special Eurobarometer 458, women in the EU are more likely than men to smoke slim cigarettes (10% vs 2%) and find slim cigarettes attractive (e.g., feminine, elegant) (20% vs. 15%)¹. Non-daily smokers and those smokers planning to quit were more likely to support a ban of slim cigarettes. This is similar to a study that found that menthol smokers who had plans to quit were more likely to support a menthol ban in comparison to those with no plans to quit¹⁶.

We found considerable country differences in reporting that slim cigarettes are less harmful, with misperceptions significantly higher in Hungary, Poland, and Romania (>25%) than in Germany (8%). Variation may be partly explained by differences in popularity of slim cigarettes. According to the 2017

Eurobarometer, use of slim cigarettes among the observed countries also varied (1% in Spain, 2% in Germany, 5% in Hungary, 6% in Greece, 6% in Romania, and 16% in Poland). Given that slim cigarettes are as harmful as other cigarettes, the high levels of misperceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful in our sample of EU smokers is concerning. However, we found some counter-intuitive results that smokers who agreed (rather than disagreed) that slim cigarettes are less harmful were more likely to support a ban on slim cigarettes. While the existing literature is limited, other studies have found harm perceptions and social norms to be associated with support for tobacco control policies and related to the choice of tobacco product used¹⁷⁻¹⁹.

While the initial draft TPD included a ban on slim cigarettes, the final version lacked such a ban. This was proposed to be due to the strong tobacco industry lobbying to dilute the regulation²⁰. As previous research has shown that smokers' perceptions are impacted by cigarette pack and stick design, and as other provisions included in the TPD were aimed at reducing misperceptions about reduced harm, results from this study further illustrate how banning slim cigarettes would support this goal^{21,22}.

While this study uses data from large representative samples of smokers from six EU Member States, there are some limitations to be considered. First, the survey did not directly ask respondents if they smoke slim cigarettes, which precluded analysis of this variable as a possible covariate. Second, the cross-sectional nature of the analysis does not allow for any

Table 2. Perceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful among smokers from six European countries, International Tobacco Control Evaluation Project Six European Country Survey Wave 2 (2018) (N=5592).

Covariate	% Slims Less Harmful			Odds Slims Less Harmful [†]		Test		
	(Unwtd Freq)	%*	(95%CI)	OR	(95%CI)	ChiSq	DF	p
Country								
Germany	(75 / 939)	8.1	(5.8, 11.3)	0.25	(0.16, 0.40)	75.19	5	<.001
Greece	(132 / 951)	13.1	(10.0, 17.0)	0.46	(0.30, 0.70)			
Hungary	(263 / 949)	29.1	(24.0, 34.8)	1.37	(0.95, 1.98)			
Poland	(290 / 947)	28.9	(24.3, 33.9)	1.13	(0.78, 1.63)			
Romania	(252 / 918)	26.8	(23.0, 31.1)	0.93	(0.64, 1.37)			
Spain	(180 / 888)	24.0	(19.5, 29.2)	1.00				
Urban/rural residence								
Urban	(405 / 1943)	21.1	(18.4, 24.2)	0.85	(0.63, 1.13)	1.61	2	0.447
Intermediate	(433 / 2137)	20.7	(18.1, 23.6)	0.95	(0.71, 1.28)			
Rural	(354 / 1512)	23.8	(20.1, 27.9)	1.00				
Sex								
Female	(624 / 2724)	23.1	(21.0, 25.3)	1.17	(1.00, 1.37)	3.71	1	0.054
Male	(568 / 2868)	20.5	(18.4, 22.8)	1.00				
Age group								
18–24	(95 / 432)	23.9	(19.3, 29.1)	0.99	(0.71, 1.37)	2.62	3	0.454
25–39	(324 / 1538)	20.9	(18.4, 23.7)	0.87	(0.69, 1.09)			
40–54	(390 / 1948)	20.8	(18.1, 23.7)	0.87	(0.71, 1.08)			
55+	(383 / 1674)	22.8	(20.2, 25.6)	1.00				
Income								
Not stated	(353 / 1555)	22.2	(19.3, 25.6)	0.88	(0.68, 1.15)	3.51	3	0.319
Low	(189 / 995)	20.1	(16.3, 24.5)	1.07	(0.77, 1.48)			
Moderate	(389 / 1801)	21.8	(19.1, 24.6)	1.11	(0.89, 1.39)			
High	(261 / 1241)	21.8	(18.8, 25.2)	1.00				
Education								
Low	(358 / 1799)	20.3	(17.6, 23.4)	0.96	(0.68, 1.38)	1.20	2	0.548
Moderate	(703 / 3129)	22.8	(20.7, 25.0)	1.08	(0.77, 1.52)			
High	(125 / 645)	19.6	(15.3, 24.8)	1.00				
Smoking status								
Daily smoker	(1153 / 5356)	21.8	(20.0, 23.7)	1.21	(0.66, 2.21)	0.37	1	0.541
Non-daily smoker	(39 / 236)	18.1	(11.8, 26.0)	1.00				

Covariate	% Slims Less Harmful			Odds Slims Less Harmful [†]		Test		
	(Unwtd Freq)	%*	(95%CI)	OR	(95%CI)	ChiSq	DF	p
Cigarettes smoked/day								
≤ 10	(456 / 2085)	22.7	(20.2, 25.3)	1.09	(0.69, 1.72)	3.82	3	0.281
11–20	(614 / 2795)	22.5	(20.2, 24.9)	1.12	(0.73, 1.73)			
21–30	(79 / 477)	13.8	(10.6, 17.9)	0.81	(0.50, 1.32)			
31+	(34 / 215)	17.2	(11.9, 23.8)	1.00				
Flavour smoked								
Menthol	(84 / 278)	26.2	(20.1, 33.5)	0.81	(0.54, 1.23)	5.09	3	0.165
Other flavour	(33 / 114)	29.1	(15.9, 45.4)	1.53	(0.75, 3.10)			
Unflavoured	(900 / 4562)	20.7	(18.8, 22.6)	0.81	(0.62, 1.07)			
No usual brand	(175 / 638)	25.3	(20.7, 30.5)	1.00				
Smokes factory-made/roll-your-own								
FM	(942 / 4175)	22.6	(20.8, 24.6)	1.31	(0.90, 1.91)	7.67	2	0.022
RYO	(180 / 1032)	19.0	(15.4, 23.3)	0.95	(0.60, 1.49)			
Both	(68 / 382)	18.1	(13.6, 23.8)	1.00				
Attempts to quit in past year								
Has not tried to quit in last 12 months	(1013 / 4782)	21.7	(19.8, 23.8)	1.17	(0.91, 1.50)	1.46	1	0.227
Tried to quit last 12 months	(178 / 804)	21.1	(18.0, 24.5)	1.00				
Plans to quit smoking								
No plans to quit	(1012 / 4974)	20.8	(19.0, 22.8)	0.73	(0.56, 0.96)	5.10	1	0.024
Plans to quit in next 6 months	(180 / 615)	28.8	(24.5, 33.6)	1.00				
Harm of own cigarette brand vs. other brands								
Don't know	(30 / 133)	21.7	(13.6, 31.7)	0.86	(0.50, 1.47)	24.22	3	<.001
A little less harmful	(240 / 804)	30.7	(26.4, 35.4)	1.77	(1.39, 2.24)			
A little more harmful	(63 / 199)	29.7	(22.9, 37.7)	1.38	(0.93, 2.07)			
No different	(858 / 4454)	19.7	(17.9, 21.7)	1.00				

* Weighted percent.

† Odds ratios from a weighted multivariable logistic regression model including all covariates listed in table.

Unwtd freq – unweighted frequency; CI – confidence interval; OR, odds ratio; ChiSq, chi-square statistic; DF – degrees of freedom.

causal conclusions. Lastly, our study relies on self-report data, which might be subject to information bias, leading to misclassification.

In conclusion, our results indicate that among a sample of smokers from six EU Member States, the percentage of smokers who support a slims ban is low, while misperceptions that

slim cigarettes are less harmful is high, particularly among countries where slim cigarette use is more prevalent. Findings of the current study provide evidence that can be used when discussing a ban on slim cigarette in order to further mitigate misperceptions that certain tobacco products are less harmful than others. The European Commission should consider this evidence in the next revision of the TPD.

Data availability

The data are jointly owned by a third party in each country that collaborates with the International Tobacco Control Policy Evaluation (ITC) Project. Data from the ITC Project are available to approved researchers two years after the date of issuance of cleaned data sets by the ITC Data Management Centre. Researchers interested in using ITC data are required to apply for approval by submitting an International Tobacco Control Data Repository (ITCDR) request application and subsequently to sign an ITCDR Data Usage Agreement. To avoid any real, potential, or perceived conflict of interest between researchers using ITC data and tobacco-related entities, no ITCDR data will be provided directly or indirectly to any researcher, institution, or consultant that is in current receipt of any grant monies or in-kind contribution from any tobacco manufacturer, distributor, or other tobacco-related entity. The criteria for data usage approval and the contents of the Data Usage Agreement are described online (<http://www.itcproject.org>). The authors of this paper obtained the data following this procedure. This is to confirm that others would be able to access these data in the same manner as the authors. The authors did not have any special access privileges that others would not have.

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Shu Xu

New York University, New York, NY, USA

The aim of this manuscript was to identify the factors that are associated with perceptions and support for a slim cigarettes ban in the EU. This review emphasized the statistical methodology and results reporting.

1. Introduction: Add a few sentences to explain why “slim cigarettes are less harmful” than cigarettes is a misperception. Explain why this is misspecification. In the same paragraph, explain what are the correct perceptions.
2. Methods.
 - To allow replication by other researchers, authors need to provide a complete and detailed introduction to all the study variables and their measures. Specifically, authors need to provide (1) a complete set of dependent and independent variables, (2) all response categories of categorical, and (3) all the response categories of a categorical variable if it was recoded. For example, it is unclear how one of the dependent variables, “support of a slim ban,” was recoded. The authors stated that the response to the original variable has three categories (i.e., “support,” “oppose,” and “don’t know.”). In another paragraph, the authors stated the response categories as “supports or strong supports,” “otherwise.” It is also unclear how these responses were recoded into binary responses (i.e., “oppose/strong oppose/don’t know”). A similar problem exists in the other dependent variable. Another example is the variable, “income.” It is unclear how the “Low,” “Moderate,” and “High” income categories were defined. This problem exists in multiple other independent variables.
 - One of the dependent variables, “perceptions that slim cigarettes are less harmful” was recoded into two response categories (agree/strongly agree that slims are less harmful v.s. neither agree nor disagree/disagree/strong disagree/don’t know). Those who responded “neither agree nor disagree” may be considered as “slim cigarette smokers are not less or more harmful than cigarettes.” However, those who “disagree/strongly disagree” considered “slim cigarette smokers are more harmful than cigarettes.” This mixture of

different responses in the reference group may lead to biased results, hence, invalid conclusions. Authors need to justify why the reference group contains multiple responses (“neither agree nor disagree/disagree/strongly disagree/don’t know”) with citations, and discuss its implication. Alternatively, authors may consider the dependent variable multi-categorical.

- If R was not used for data analysis, then remove the following sentence. “The analyses can be done in most software packages that handle complex data design, such as R, an open-access software, using the ‘svytable” and “svyglm” commands from the survey package.”
- Add 1-2 sentences to explain the size of the study sample, and how the authors handled missing data.

3. Results.

- Add one paragraph summarizing the characteristics of the study sample.
- Replace “OR” with “aOR” in text and Tables 1 & 2 because multivariable logistic regressions were conducted. Update the footnotes accordingly.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

No

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Partly

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Partly

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: My area is biostatistics. This review emphasized the statistical methodology and results reporting.

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to state that I do not consider it to be of an acceptable scientific standard, for reasons outlined above.

Reviewer Report 05 April 2022

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Anish Thekkumkara Surendran Nair

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It is a well written article based on ITC6E data.

However, the following points may be addressed

1. Under 'Methods' section, it is written that "Once a respondent was selected, an information letter was provided and consent was taken". But the selection criteria was not clearly mentioned.
2. It is given that "The primary outcome of this study, support for a ban on slim cigarettes, was assessed with the question: "Would you support or oppose a law that banned all slim cigarettes, that is, those cigarettes that are slimmer in size than regular cigarettes?" (support; oppose; don't know)". But it is not clear that how this variable was used in analysis. Is it support vs non-support, counting 'don't know' category also along with 'oppose' group.
3. Last part of 'Methods' session, it is given that "The analyses can be done in most software packages that handle complex data design, such as R, an open-access software, using the 'svytable' and "svyglm" commands from the survey package." It is not clear whether the investigators used the statistical package. If not, this sentence could be deleted.

Is the work clearly and accurately presented and does it cite the current literature?

Yes

Is the study design appropriate and does the work have academic merit?

Yes

Are sufficient details of methods and analysis provided to allow replication by others?

Yes

If applicable, is the statistical analysis and its interpretation appropriate?

Partly

Are all the source data underlying the results available to ensure full reproducibility?

Yes

Are the conclusions drawn adequately supported by the results?

Yes

Competing Interests: No competing interests were disclosed.

Reviewer Expertise: Public Health and Epidemiology

I confirm that I have read this submission and believe that I have an appropriate level of expertise to confirm that it is of an acceptable scientific standard, however I have significant reservations, as outlined above.
